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ABSTRACT

Electrical detection of graphene plasmons is important for developing mid-infrared photodetection and sensing applications based on graphene. Here, we theoretically investigate a configuration based on graphene nanoribbons on silicon, forming a series of Schottky junctions. We calculate the heating up of charge carriers in graphene, following plasmon decay, and their thermionic emission across the junctions leading to the generation of photocurrent. We extract an external responsivity up to ≈ 110 mA/W with a corresponding noise equivalent power ≈ 190 pW/Hz^{0.5}, specific detectivity $D^* \approx 4 \times 10^6$ Jones, and response time ≈ 12 ns. We further demonstrate how this platform can be used for developing label free chemical sensors, utilizing surface enhanced infrared absorption, where the analyte presence is directly monitored by the photocurrent change. The methods and conclusions derived in this work are applicable throughout the infrared spectrum, where graphene plasmons can be realized.

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Surface plasmon polaritons (SPPs) in single layer graphene (SLG)^{1–5} are a promising platform for light detection,^{6–13} optical modulation,^{14–16} and sensing applications.^{17–22} SLG-SPPs are gate-tunable throughout the infrared (IR),^{23–25} sensitive to chemical doping,²⁶ and exhibit high spatial field confinement.^{1,17,27,28} The latter is a result of significant momentum mismatch between SLG-SPP and free-space light,^{2,4} which, however, also renders the light in-coupling to SLG-SPPs inefficient due to momentum conservation.^{2,4} Techniques to match momenta and increase in-coupling efficiency include SNOM assisted scattering,^{24,25} scattering from metallic-nanoparticles,^{29–31} and nanostructured SLG, e.g., in the form of nanodisks^{32–37} or nanoribbons.^{23,38–42}

Detection of SLG-SPPs is typically done optically and is indirect, i.e., by spectral measurements on the reflected and transmitted light,^{15,17–19,23,35–37,39} followed by post-processing and simulations to identify and subtract background absorption and peaks coming from other device elements, such as metallic antennas and Fabry-Pérot

cavities. An electrical measurement technique yielding direct information on SLG-SPP excitation, however, would be ideal for reasons both fundamental (understanding of the excitation and decay mechanisms) and practical (clear distinction between SLG-SPPs and other device resonances, avoidance of bulky optics). There have been several studies addressing electrical detection of SLG-SPPs. In all of them, the elevated SLG electronic temperature at plasmon resonance is utilized to induce and harvest a photocurrent.^{7–13} One approach involves the photo-thermoelectric effect (PTE).⁷ In Ref. 7, an external responsivity (R_{ext}) of 20 mA/W was measured at zero bias, with a calculated noise equivalent power (NEP) of 400 pW/Hz^{0.5}. Another approach involves the temperature-induced changes in SLG conductivity.^{8–10} However, this requires electrically biasing SLG, which introduces significant dark current noise (SLG is a conductor). A further bottleneck is also related to the weak temperature dependence of SLG conductivity,⁴³ especially in chemical vapor deposition (CVD) graphene where carrier transport is dominated by defects and grain boundaries.^{44,45} As a result, the

measured R_{ext} in Ref. 10 was found in the order of $R_{ext} \approx 10 \mu\text{A}/\text{W}$. An improvement, utilizing the conductivity change due to elevated SLG carrier temperature mechanism, was reported in Ref. 9, using graphene disk plasmonic resonators (GDPRs)^{8,9} connected with graphene nanoribbons (GNRs), whereby the GDPRs generate hot carriers population via plasmon resonant absorption and thermalization, while carrier transport is thermally activated along the GNRs. This work resulted in measuring $R_{ext} \approx 16 \text{ mA}/\text{W}$,⁹ with a measured NEP $\approx 1.3 \text{ nW}/\text{Hz}^{0.5}$, and a theoretical lower limit⁹ of NEP calculated at $\approx 460 \text{ pW}/\text{Hz}^{0.5}$. An improved configuration was reported by Safaei *et al.*,¹¹ with a high voltage responsivity of $\sim 2500 \text{ V}/\text{W}$ and low NEP of $\sim 7 \text{ pW}/\text{Hz}^{0.5}$, exploiting the PTE effect in an asymmetrically patterned graphene configuration, where plasmons are excited and absorbed at one side of an electrically biased graphene layer. Using similar configurations, Shabir *et al.* also reported similar performances,^{12,13} reaching responsivities in the order of $\sim 10^5 \text{ V}/\text{W}$ and NEP as low as $\sim 10 \text{ fW}/\text{Hz}^{0.5}$. The latter approaches, however, also rely on applying a source–drain bias across the SLG channel.^{8,9,11–13}

Here, we propose and theoretically investigate an unbiased SLG/*p*-Si Schottky junction configuration, operating in the thermionic regime,^{46,47} as a platform for electrical detection of SLG-SPPs. We assume a periodic array of SLG-GNR on top of a *p*-doped silicon substrate (*p*-Si) forming a series of SLG/*p*-Si Schottky contacts,^{46,48,49} where graphene plasmon resonance frequency scales with nanoribbon width^{27,41} and can be tuned by gating⁵⁰ and/or reverse voltage bias.^{51,52} The absorbed optical power in GNR, promoted by SPPs excitation, leads to a thermalized hot carrier gas in SLG,^{7–9,53} which in turn creates photocurrent via thermionic emission across the SLG/*p*-Si junction.^{46,47} We extend our theoretical framework, which was developed in Ref. 46 for inter-band optical excitation in SLG with photons energy $E_{ph} > 2E_F$, to the intra-band absorption process at longer wavelengths (i.e., at Pauli blocking regime $E_{ph} < 2E_F$), and show that GNR-SPPs based Schottky junctions can produce significant photocurrent. Specifically, using optimized device geometry and realistic operational parameters, we calculate an external responsivity $R_{ext} \approx 110 \text{ mA}/\text{W}$, with a NEP $\approx 190 \text{ pW}/\text{Hz}^{0.5}$. We demonstrate this electrical detection scheme in a chemical sensing application, utilizing the surface enhanced infrared absorption technique (SEIRA)^{17–21,54–57} and assuming toluene⁵⁸ as an analyte paradigm. We optimize the sensor device architecture and operational parameters and explore its detection and sensitivity limits.

We consider a periodic GNR array of width w and period L on top of a *p*-Si substrate ($N_{A,\text{Si}} = 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$), forming a Schottky junction,^{46,48} as depicted in Fig. 1(a). We assume the GNRs to be *p*-doped, as is common in CVD fabricated graphene,^{59,60} and a fixed $w/L = 0.5$ ratio for simplicity. The structure is supplemented by an Au backmirror at spacer distance $d = 1 \mu\text{m}$, to form a Fabry–Pérot cavity and enhance light absorption.^{15,17,54} The lowest energy GNR-SPP resonant wavelength can be calculated by^{27,41,42} $\lambda_{\text{res}} = \alpha [(1 + \epsilon_{r,\text{Si}})\epsilon_0 w/E_F]^{1/2}$, where $\alpha = \eta (2\pi\hbar c/e)$, \hbar is the reduced Planck constant, c is the speed of light, e is the electron charge, E_F is the SLG Fermi level, ϵ_0 and $\epsilon_{r,\text{Si}} = 11.7$ are the free space and relative permittivity⁶¹ of the *p*-Si substrate, respectively. The prefactor η accounts for the hybridization and redshift⁴² of plasmons in neighboring GNRs, where $\eta \rightarrow 1$ for large ($w/L \rightarrow 0$) GNR separations. η can also be affected by SPP-cavity interactions with the backmirror.⁵⁴ Here, the value $\eta = 1.25$ is extracted by fitting the relationship for λ_{res} to the finite difference time

FIG. 1. (a) Schematic of the proposed structure. A PAGR array of width w and period $L = 2w$ is placed on a *p*-Si substrate with an Au backmirror at a distance of $d = 1 \mu\text{m}$. A thin layer of toluene (transparent red) is assumed to cover the whole PAGR. (b) Calculated SLG absorption for $w = 40 \text{ nm}$, $E_F \approx -0.36 \text{ eV}$, $\tau_{\text{opt}} = 40 \text{ fs}$ with (dashed) and without (continuous) the 8 nm thick toluene layer. The vertical gray lines mark the absorption lines of toluene.

domain⁶² (FDTD) calculations of the proposed structure (see the [supplementary material](#)). By adjusting E_F and/or w , the GNR-SPP resonance can be tuned within the application desired wavelength range (e.g., for toluene sensing we target $\lambda \approx 13 - 15 \mu\text{m}$). Assuming $w = 40 \text{ nm}$ (more w values will also be explored), the required SNR doping level is $E_F \approx -0.36 \text{ eV}$. The free carriers relaxation time in SLG, τ_{opt} , depends on E_F and carrier mobility μ_q via^{63,64} $\tau_{\text{opt}} = \mu_q E_F / ev_F^2$, where $v_F = 10^6 \text{ m/s}$ is the SLG Fermi velocity⁴⁸ and is typically in the order of $\sim 100 \text{ fs}$ ⁶⁴ for polycrystalline CVD graphene. For GNR, we assume τ_{opt} to be w -limited,⁶⁵ i.e., $\tau_{\text{opt}} = w/v_F = 40 \text{ fs}$. This yields mobility $\mu_q \approx 1000 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, similar to what expected for defected and/or nanostructured SLG.^{54,65} The optical conductivity of the GNRs is modeled by the Kubo formula,^{66,67} and the device optical response is simulated by the FDTD method⁶² using the Lumerical FDTD solver.⁶⁸ Under IR illumination, the calculated GNR-SPP absorption coefficient is plotted in Fig. 1(b), reaching a maximum of $\sim 60\%$.

Regarding the sensing application, toluene has two main absorption lines at $\lambda_1 = 13.7 \mu\text{m}$ and $\lambda_2 = 14.4 \mu\text{m}$.⁵⁸ These spectral features are poorly probed directly by light, due to the large mismatch between resonant wavelength ($>10 \mu\text{m}$) and molecular size ($<\text{nm}$).^{18,55} The principle of SEIRA is to use the deep sub-wavelength electric field (E-field) confinement and intensity enhancement of the SPP mode in GNR^{17–21,54–57} to probe these vibrational fingerprints. If a thin $d_{\text{tol}} = 8 \text{ nm}$ toluene layer (more d_{tol} values will also be explored) is placed on top of GNR, the latter's absorption will be reduced at the spectral lines of toluene peaks, as shown in Fig. 1(b). This

also involves a small redshift of the overall response, due to the different dielectric environment introduced by the toluene layer.¹⁸ We next evaluate the thermionic photocurrents, induced by the GNR-SPP light absorption.

Upon GNR/*p*-Si contact, holes will flow from *p*-Si to GNRs due to their work function difference,^{46,48,51} forming a depletion layer in *p*-Si and a Schottky junction with barrier height^{46,48} ($\Phi_B = eV_0 + e\phi_{Si}$, where V_0 is the built-in potential across the depletion layer^{46,48} and $e\phi_{Si}$ is the energy difference between the Fermi level $E_{F,Si}$ in Si and the valence band $E_{V,Si}$.^{46,51} Using the framework developed in Ref. 46 (see also the [supplementary material](#)), we find that for $E_F = -0.36$ eV, the GNRs must initially (before contact) be at $E_F^* = -0.35$ eV, i.e., no significant E_F shift occurs. This is related to the increased density of states of SLG at elevated E_F values.⁴⁶ At the contact, GNR/*p*-Si Schottky junction gives rise to a Schottky barrier height (SBH) $\Phi_B \sim 0.31$ eV. In this work, we will not consider reverse bias, thus avoiding dark current and excess noise.⁴⁶

We assume that the incident IR light is continuous (or quasi-continuous, e.g., in long \gg ps pulses⁴⁶) and quasi-monochromatic, i.e., filtered by a grating or prism.⁶⁹ After light absorption, the excited GNR carriers thermalize within ~ 20 fs^{70,71} and eventually cool down through the emission of acoustical and optical phonons.^{46,70–81} During this process, an elevated electronic temperature is achieved and additional fraction of charge carriers at the Fermi-Dirac distribution tail will overcome the SBH⁴⁶ and thermionically will be injected into *p*-Si. The latter will contribute to further cooling^{46,82} as well as a net photocurrent across the junction.^{46,47} To calculate the electronic temperature $T_{e,SLG}$ of charge carriers in GNR under continuous illumination, we use the framework developed in Ref. 46 (see also the [supplementary material](#)) and self-consistently solve the equilibrium equation for $T_{e,SLG}$:

$$\alpha_{SLG} P_{in}/S = J_{e-ph} + J_{th}, \quad (1)$$

where P_{in} is the incident optical power focused in area S (here taken as the diffraction limited spot $S = \lambda^2/\pi \approx 6 \times 10^{-7}$ cm², where $\lambda = 14$ μ m is the average wavelength of interest) and $\alpha_{SLG} \equiv \alpha_{SLG}(E_F, T_{e,SLG})$ is the absorption coefficient of the GNRs. $J_{e-ph} \equiv J_{e-ph}(E_F, T_{e,SLG})$ is the thermal current density dissipated into the phonon bath via electron-phonon (e-ph) interactions,⁴⁶ and $J_{th} \equiv J_{th}(E_F, T_{e,SLG})$ is the thermal current density across the junction,^{46,82} for each GNR. For J_{e-ph} , we consider two main e-ph scattering processes: optical phonons^{74–76} and acoustic phonons via disorder-assisted supercollisions.^{77–80} For the former, we consider two branches,⁴⁶ at the K-point^{83–85} ($\Omega_K = 161$ meV) and at the doubly degenerate Γ -point^{83–85} ($\Omega_\Gamma = 196$ meV) of the SLG Brillouin zone. For the latter, we assume a concentration of short-range scatterers with a mean free path l .^{46,77–80} For the GNR structure, we assume l to be w -limited, i.e., $l = w$. The combined contributions then lead to an effective e-ph relaxation time $\tau_{e-ph} = c_v \Delta T_{e,SLG} / J_{e-ph} \sim 400$ fs, where $\Delta T_{e,SLG}$ is the electronic temperature rise at equilibrium ($\Delta T_{e,SLG} \ll T_0 = 300$ K) and $c_v(E_F, T_{e,SLG})$ is the electronic heat capacity.⁴⁶ This τ_{e-ph} value is much lower compared to the one for a continuous SLG sheet (~ 1.5 ps)⁴⁶ due to the smaller mean free path l , which renders supercollision as the dominant cooling process for GNRs. We note that here we examine only the linear regime,⁴⁶ i.e., low enough P_{in} so that $\Delta T_{e,SLG}$ values are in the order of mK. Due to the much larger ($\times 10^3$) heat capacity of the SLG lattice compared to that of its

carriers,⁸⁶ we assume the lattice temperature to be fixed at $T_{l,SLG} = 300$ K.

The thermionic electrical and thermal current densities across the Schottky junction are calculated using the Landauer transport formalism:^{46–49,82}

$$J_{el}(E_F, T_{e,SLG}) = -\frac{e}{\tau_{inj}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \nu(\epsilon) \mathcal{T}(\epsilon) \mathcal{D}f(\epsilon) d\epsilon, \quad (2a)$$

$$J_{th}(E_F, T_{e,SLG}) = \frac{1}{\tau_{inj}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \nu(\epsilon) (\epsilon - \mu_{SLG}) \mathcal{T}(\epsilon) \mathcal{D}f(\epsilon) d\epsilon, \quad (2b)$$

where τ_{inj} is the effective injection time of charge carriers from SLG to Si,^{46–49} $\nu(\epsilon) = 2|\epsilon|/(\pi\hbar^2 u_F^2)$ is the graphene carrier density of states, and $\mathcal{D}f(\epsilon) = f_{FD}(\epsilon; \mu_{SLG}, T_{e,SLG}) - f_{FD}(\epsilon; \mu_{Si}, T_{e,Si})$ with $f_{FD}(\epsilon; \mu, T) = \{\exp[(\epsilon - \mu)/(k_B T)] + 1\}^{-1}$ being the Fermi-Dirac distribution at chemical potential μ and temperature T . $\mathcal{T}(\epsilon)$ is the probability of charge carrier transmission from SLG to Si over Φ_B^{CNP} , where Φ_B^{CNP} is the SBH with respect to the charge neutrality point⁴⁶ (for simplicity, we assume $\mathcal{T}(\epsilon) = 1$ for $\epsilon > \Phi_B^{CNP}$ and zero otherwise^{46–48}). τ_{inj} varies with SLG quality,^{48,49} Schottky interface quality,^{47,51,87} momentum conservation/relaxation at the junction,^{88–90} and E_F and $T_{e,SLG}$.^{88–90} A lower bound for τ_{inj} can be estimated for the low temperature regime ($k_B T_{e,SLG} \ll E_F$) using⁸⁹ $\tau_{inj} \sim \hbar|E_F|/(k_B T_{e,SLG})^2$ yielding $\tau_{inj} \approx 350$ fs for $E_F = -0.36$ eV and $T_{e,SLG} \approx 300$ K.

The photocurrent across the junction is calculated as $I_{ph} = J_{el} S/2$. (the 1/2 factor is because of half-coverage, i.e., $w/L = 0.5$.) We assume incident power $P_{in} \approx 9.35$ nW. This yields an external responsivity (calculated at $\lambda = 14$ μ m) $R_{ext} \approx 1$ mA/W with a noise equivalent power NEP ≈ 1.4 nW/Hz^{0.5}. The specific detectivity, defined as⁶¹ $D^* = \sqrt{S}/NEP$, is extracted having a value $D^* = 5.5 \approx 10^5$ Jones. This configuration has a response time of $\tau_{resp} \approx 5$ ns with a cutoff frequency ≈ 1.22 GHz (see the [supplementary material](#)). Upon analyte placement, assuming analyte thickness $d_{tot} = 8$ nm, the chemical sensing signal I_S is determined by the photocurrent difference, $I_S \equiv \Delta I_{ph} = I_{ph,bare} - I_{ph,toluene}$, which is plotted in Fig. 2(a), showing peaks at the toluene molecular resonances. The peak at $\lambda_1 = 13.7$ μ m is higher due to this mode's stronger absorptivity.⁵⁸ Quantitative comparison between peaks can be done after subtraction of the baseline [red dashed line in Fig. 2(a)]. By operating the SLG/Si Schottky diode at zero bias, with eliminated dark current, the noise signal (normalized to a 1 Hz spectral band) is $\langle i_S^2 \rangle = \langle i_{sh}^2 \rangle + \langle i_J^2 \rangle$, where $\langle i_{sh}^2 \rangle = 2e I_{ph}$ is the shot noise contribution⁶¹ and $\langle i_J^2 \rangle = 4k_B T_{e,SLG}/R_{eq}$ is the Johnson (thermal) noise contribution,⁶¹ where $R_{eq} = dV/dI_{ph}$ is the diode shunt resistance.^{46,61} The latter is calculated through the inverse of the derivative of the dark current with respect to applied bias, for low (\sim mV) reverse bias values.⁴⁶

For chemical sensing, when measuring a signal I_S , the effective total noise is contributed by both $I_{ph,bare}$ and $I_{ph,toluene}$, i.e., the total noise power is $\langle i_{S,tot}^2 \rangle = \langle i_{S,bare}^2 \rangle + \langle i_{S,toluene}^2 \rangle$. To quantify a limit of detection associated with the photo-thermionic process, we calculate the minimum optical power P_{min} needed, i.e., signal to noise ratio SNR = 1, in order to detect the presence of an analyte. We define SNR, for each absorption line of the analyte, as $SNR = I_S/i_{S,tot}$. In the proposed device, we find that the main contribution to $i_{S,tot}$ is the Johnson noise, where the calculated $i_J \gg i_{sh}$ is in the order of few pA and few fA, respectively. Since Johnson noise does not depend on P_{in} ,^{46,61} SNR can be approximated to scale linearly with the incident

FIG. 2. Photocurrent difference (I_s) spectrum as calculated after the subtraction of I_{ph} spectra without and with toluene, assuming toluene thickness $d_{tol} = 8$ nm. The red dashed line marks the baseline of the spectrum.

optical power, given the large (more than five decades) linear dynamical range (LDR) of SLG/Si Schottky junctions operating in the photo-thermionic regime.⁴⁶ Hence, $SNR = \alpha P_{in}$, where α is a proportion coefficient. As a result, the limit of detection at $SNR = 1$ is $P_{min} = 1/\alpha$. We calculated the power dependence of SNR for each absorption line of toluene, assuming $d_{tol} = 8$ nm (see the [supplementary material](#)), and found from the slope $\alpha_1 \approx 0.14$ nW⁻¹ and $\alpha_2 \approx 0.10$ nW⁻¹, where the subscript denotes the $\lambda_1 = 13.7$ μ m and $\lambda_2 = 14.4$ μ m lines, respectively. The corresponding limits of detection are $P_{min,1} \approx 7.1$ and $P_{min,2} \approx 10$ nW, respectively.

Next, we study the effect of the various operational parameters on P_{min} . We first explore the effect of E_F . Besides changing the SBH, E_F variations also require the reevaluation of several other quantities, like the τ_{inj} lower bound, the width w to keep the GNR-SPP frequency fixed, the free carrier relaxation time τ_{opt} , and the mean free path l for supercollision scattering. These parameters are summarized in [Table I](#) for three different values of E_F .

[Figure 3\(a\)](#) plots P_{min} calculations assuming different E_F s using the parameters as for [Table I](#). Higher E_F (and w) values lead to lower P_{min} , i.e., detection capability at lower incident optical power. This is because increasing E_F brings to: (a) smaller SBH, which triggers an enhanced thermionic emission across SLG/Si Schottky interface and (b) larger w , which leads to longer τ_{opt} , increased intraband SLG conductivity and higher light absorption, as well as larger supercollision mean free path l and, thus, less cooling, yielding higher $T_{e,SLG}$ for the

TABLE I. Values of the parameters assumed in our calculations. Initial (before contact with p -Si) E_F^i , SLG E_F after Schottky junction formation, SBH Φ_B , carrier injection time τ_{inj} , free carrier relaxation time τ_{opt} , PAGR width w and mean free path for supercollision scattering l .

E_F^i (eV)	-0.250	-0.350	-0.500
E_F (eV)	-0.265	-0.358	-0.502
Φ_B (eV)	0.408	0.314	0.169
τ_{inj} (fs)	260	350	490
τ_{opt} (fs)	30	40	55
w (nm)	30	40	55
l (nm)	30	40	55

FIG. 3. (a) Calculated P_{min} for different values of $E_F - w$. (b) P_{min} as a function of d_{tol} . In both cases we used the parameters as in the second column of [Table I](#).

same P_{in} . A slight counterbalance comes from the longer τ_{inj} , as shown in [Table I](#). The overall trend, however, remains that of a lower P_{min} for larger E_F values. The performance differences, upon changing E_F , can also be understood by the R_{ext} and NEP values. At the central wavelength, the lower graphene doping (e.g., $E_F = -0.265$ eV), which is attributed to higher SBH ([Table I](#)), results in $R_{ext} \approx 40$ μ A/W, $NEP \approx 7.4$ nW/Hz^{0.5}, $D^* \approx 10^5$ Jones, and response time $\tau_{resp} \approx 4.9$ ns. For higher SLG doping ($E_F = -0.50$ eV, i.e., lower SBH), R_{ext} increases and reaches $R_{ext} \approx 110$ mA/W with a lower $NEP \approx 190$ pW/Hz^{0.5}, $D^* \approx 4 \times 10^6$ Jones, and response time $\tau_{resp} \approx 12$ ns. There is, however, a lower limit of a SBH that can be achieved in the given configuration in the order of $\Phi_B^{min} \approx eV_0$ that depends on Si doping [see the [supplementary material](#), Eq. (S3)]. The latter would allow achieving lower Φ_B^{min} using higher p -Si doping but would also lead to a fraction of light loss in Si (due to free carrier absorption), thus lowering the SLG carrier temperature increase and associated thermionic current across the Schottky junctions. Note also that a reduced ambient temperature will not improve performance. Because of the thermionic nature of the photocurrent generation, the responsivity will get strongly suppressed at lower temperatures⁴⁶ [see also Eq. 2(a)] and result in a NEP increase despite the reduction of the Johnson noise.

Up to now, we have assumed a toluene layer with thickness $d_{tol} = 8$ nm. We next calculate the P_{min} as a function of d_{tol} , assuming $E_F \approx -0.36$ eV (and the corresponding operational parameters in [Table I](#)), and plot it in [Fig. 3\(b\)](#). For vanishing toluene thickness, P_{min} is increased, i.e., higher optical power is needed to detect a thinner

layer of the analyte. On the contrary, P_{min} plateaus after $d_{tol} \sim 35$ nm. This is due to SPP fields extending only a few tens of nm away from the GNRs.^{17–21,54–57} Further increase in d_{tol} does not change the overall I_{ph} yield, highlighting the significance and major impact of surface-enhanced fields of GNR SPPs to directly and electrically probe the toluene's (or other analytes) absorption lines.

In conclusion, we have theoretically studied the use of GNRs in a SLG/Si Schottky junction configuration, to electrically detect graphene plasmons. Using the computational framework developed in Ref. 46, and realistic considerations for all material and device parameters involved, our calculations suggest an increased I_{ph} yield at the SPP resonant wavelengths. Optimized devices can reach external responsivity ≈ 110 mA/W with a corresponding NEP ≈ 190 pW/Hz^{0.5}, D^* $\approx 4 \times 10^6$ Jones, and response time $\tau_{resp} \approx 12$ ns, corresponding to a cutoff frequency of ≈ 0.5 GHz. This platform for electrical detection of SLG plasmons can operate either as a mid-IR photodetector or as a chemical sensor for analyte detection via the SEIRA technique. We studied the operation of such a sensor and extracted quantitative relations for its detection and sensitivity limits. The methods and conclusions derived in this work are applicable throughout the IR, where SLG SPPs can be realized. Limitations in reaching shorter wavelengths may arise due to fabrication constraints in reducing w and reaching large E_F values, as well as material availability in utilizing a semiconducting substrates with smaller dielectric constants. Assuming $w_{min} \approx 20$ nm and $E_{F,max} \approx 0.55$ eV for p -Si with $N_{A,Si} = 10^{17}$ cm⁻³, there is a lower bound at $\lambda \approx 8$ μ m. There is no limitation, however, for longer wavelengths, since w can always be increased/tuned accordingly, and the proposed scheme is based on thermionic emission, which is not limited by the substrate's bandgap. This work facilitates the theoretical background for a unique tunable multi-band optics-free photodetector and/or chemical sensor based on graphene plasmons.

See the [supplementary material](#) for details in FDTD simulations, Schottky junction formation, absorbed power and carrier cooling calculations, temporal response of the proposed device, and SNR dependence on input power.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Spyros Doukas: Conceptualization (equal); Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Software (equal); Validation (equal); Visualization (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review and editing (equal). **Prateeksha Sharma:** Data curation (supporting); Formal analysis (supporting); Software (supporting). **Ilya Goykhman:** Conceptualization (equal); Funding acquisition (equal); Methodology (equal); Project administration (equal); Validation (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review and editing (equal). **Eleferios Lidorikis:**

Conceptualization (lead); Funding acquisition (lead); Methodology (lead); Project administration (lead); Supervision (lead); Validation (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review and editing (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

REFERENCES

- 1F. H. Koppens, D. E. Chang, and F. J. García de Abajo, “Graphene plasmonics: A platform for strong light–matter interactions,” *Nano Lett.* **11**, 3370–3377 (2011).
- 2A. N. Grigorenko, M. Polini, and K. Novoselov, “Graphene plasmonics,” *Nat. Photonics* **6**, 749–758 (2012).
- 3F. J. Garcia de Abajo, “Graphene plasmonics: Challenges and opportunities,” *ACS Photonics* **1**, 135–152 (2014).
- 4P. A. D. Gonçalves and N. M. Peres, *An Introduction to Graphene Plasmonics* (World Scientific, 2016).
- 5T. Low and P. Avouris, “Graphene plasmonics for terahertz to mid-infrared applications,” *ACS Nano* **8**, 1086–1101 (2014).
- 6I. Torre, A. Tomadin, R. Krahne, V. Pellegrini, and M. Polini, “Electrical plasmon detection in graphene waveguides,” *Phys. Rev. B* **91**, 081402 (2015).
- 7M. B. Lundeberg, Y. Gao, A. Woessner, C. Tan, P. Alonso-González, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, J. Hone, R. Hillenbrand, and F. H. Koppens, “Thermoelectric detection and imaging of propagating graphene plasmons,” *Nat. Mater.* **16**, 204–207 (2017).
- 8R. Yu and F. J. Garcia de Abajo, “Electrical detection of single graphene plasmons,” *ACS Nano* **10**, 8045–8053 (2016).
- 9Q. Guo, R. Yu, C. Li, S. Yuan, B. Deng, F. J. G. de Abajo, and F. Xia, “Efficient electrical detection of mid-infrared graphene plasmons at room temperature,” *Nat. Mater.* **17**, 986–992 (2018).
- 10M. Freitag, T. Low, W. Zhu, H. Yan, F. Xia, and P. Avouris, “Photocurrent in graphene harnessed by tunable intrinsic plasmons,” *Nat. Commun.* **4**, 1951 (2013).
- 11A. Safaei, S. Chandra, M. W. Shabbir, M. N. Leuenberger, and D. Chanda, “Dirac plasmon-assisted asymmetric hot carrier generation for room-temperature infrared detection,” *Nat. Commun.* **10**, 3498 (2019).
- 12M. W. Shabbir, S. Chandra, and M. N. Leuenberger, “Numerical simulations of nanolayered heterostructures of nanopatterned graphene and vanadium oxide for mid-infrared photodetectors operating close to room temperature,” *ACS Appl. Nano Mater.* **5**, 2094–2101 (2022).
- 13M. W. Shabbir and M. N. Leuenberger, “Theoretical model of a plasmonically enhanced tunable spectrally selective infrared photodetector based on intercalation-doped nanopatterned multilayer graphene,” *ACS Nano* **16**, 5529–5536 (2022).
- 14V. W. Brar, M. S. Jang, M. Sherrott, J. J. Lopez, and H. A. Atwater, “Highly confined tunable mid-infrared plasmonics in graphene nanoresonators,” *Nano Lett.* **13**, 2541–2547 (2013).
- 15M. S. Jang, V. W. Brar, M. C. Sherrott, J. J. Lopez, L. Kim, S. Kim, M. Choi, H. A. Atwater *et al.*, “Tunable large resonant absorption in a midinfrared graphene Salisbury screen,” *Phys. Rev. B* **90**, 165409 (2014).
- 16S. Kim, M. S. Jang, V. W. Brar, K. W. Mauser, L. Kim, and H. A. Atwater, “Electronically tunable perfect absorption in graphene,” *Nano Lett.* **18**, 971–979 (2018).
- 17Y. Li, H. Yan, D. B. Farmer, X. Meng, W. Zhu, R. M. Osgood, T. F. Heinz, and P. Avouris, “Graphene plasmon enhanced vibrational sensing of surface-adsorbed layers,” *Nano Lett.* **14**, 1573–1577 (2014).
- 18D. Rodrigo, O. Limaj, D. Janner, D. Etezadi, F. J. G. De Abajo, V. Pruneri, and H. Altug, “Mid-infrared plasmonic biosensing with graphene,” *Science* **349**, 165–168 (2015).
- 19D. B. Farmer, P. Avouris, Y. Li, T. F. Heinz, and S.-J. Han, “Ultrasensitive plasmonic detection of molecules with graphene,” *ACS Photonics* **3**, 553–557 (2016).

- ²⁰A. Marini, I. Silveiro, and F. J. Garcia de Abajo, "Molecular sensing with tunable graphene plasmons," *ACS Photonics* **2**, 876–882 (2015).
- ²¹H. Hu, X. Yang, X. Guo, K. Khaliji, S. R. Biswas, F. J. G. de Abajo, T. Low, Z. Sun, and Q. Dai, "Gas identification with graphene plasmons," *Nat. Commun.* **10**, 1131 (2019).
- ²²S. Ogawa, S. Fukushima, and M. Shimatani, "Graphene plasmonics in sensor applications: A review," *Sensors* **20**, 3563 (2020).
- ²³L. Ju, B. Geng, J. Horng, C. Girit, M. Martin, Z. Hao, H. A. Bechtel, X. Liang, A. Zettl, Y. R. Shen *et al.*, "Graphene plasmonics for tunable terahertz metamaterials," *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **6**, 630–634 (2011).
- ²⁴Z. Fei, A. Rodin, G. O. Andreev, W. Bao, A. McLeod, M. Wagner, L. Zhang, Z. Zhao, M. Thiemens, G. Dominguez *et al.*, "Gate-tuning of graphene plasmons revealed by infrared nano-imaging," *Nature* **487**, 82–85 (2012).
- ²⁵J. Chen, M. Badioli, P. Alonso-González, S. Thongrattanasiri, F. Huth, J. Osmond, M. Spasenović, A. Centeno, A. Pesquera, P. Godignon *et al.*, "Optical nano-imaging of gate-tunable graphene plasmons," *Nature* **487**, 77–81 (2012).
- ²⁶H. Liu, Y. Liu, and D. Zhu, "Chemical doping of graphene," *J. Mater. Chem.* **21**, 3335–3345 (2011).
- ²⁷B. Vasić, G. Isić, and R. Gajić, "Localized surface plasmon resonances in graphene ribbon arrays for sensing of dielectric environment at infrared frequencies," *J. Appl. Phys.* **113**, 013110 (2013).
- ²⁸P. Li, T. Wang, H. Bockmann, and T. Taubner, "Graphene-enhanced infrared near-field microscopy," *Nano Lett.* **14**, 4400–4405 (2014).
- ²⁹D. K. Polyushkin, J. Milton, S. Santandrea, S. Russo, M. F. Craciun, S. J. Green, L. Mahe, C. P. Winolve, and W. L. Barnes, "Graphene as a substrate for plasmonic nanoparticles," *J. Opt.* **15**, 114001 (2013).
- ³⁰P. Alonso-González, A. Y. Nikitin, F. Golmar, A. Centeno, A. Pesquera, S. Vélez, J. Chen, G. Navickaite, F. Koppens, A. Zurutuza *et al.*, "Controlling graphene plasmons with resonant metal antennas and spatial conductivity patterns," *Science* **344**, 1369–1373 (2014).
- ³¹T. Echtermeyer, S. Milana, U. Sassi, A. Eiden, M. Wu, E. Lidorikis, and A. Ferrari, "Surface plasmon polariton graphene photodetectors," *Nano Lett.* **16**, 8–20 (2016).
- ³²Z. Wang, T. Li, K. Almdal, N. A. Mortensen, S. Xiao, and S. Ndoni, "Experimental demonstration of graphene plasmons working close to the near-infrared window," *Opt. Lett.* **41**, 5345–5348 (2016).
- ³³H. Yan, X. Li, B. Chandra, G. Tulevski, Y. Wu, M. Freitag, W. Zhu, P. Avouris, and F. Xia, "Tunable infrared plasmonic devices using graphene/insulator stacks," *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **7**, 330–334 (2012).
- ³⁴S. Thongrattanasiri, F. H. Koppens, and F. J. G. De Abajo, "Complete optical absorption in periodically patterned graphene," *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **108**, 047401 (2012).
- ³⁵Z. Fang, S. Thongrattanasiri, A. Schlather, Z. Liu, L. Ma, Y. Wang, P. M. Ajayan, P. Nordlander, N. J. Halas, and F. J. García de Abajo, "Gated tunability and hybridization of localized plasmons in nanostructured graphene," *ACS Nano* **7**, 2388–2395 (2013).
- ³⁶Z. Fang, Y. Wang, A. E. Schlather, Z. Liu, P. M. Ajayan, F. J. García de Abajo, P. Nordlander, X. Zhu, and N. J. Halas, "Active tunable absorption enhancement with graphene nanodisk arrays," *Nano Lett.* **14**, 299–304 (2014).
- ³⁷X. Zhu, W. Wang, W. Yan, M. B. Larsen, P. Bøggild, T. G. Pedersen, S. Xiao, J. Zi, and N. A. Mortensen, "Plasmon-phonon coupling in large-area graphene dot and antidot arrays fabricated by nanosphere lithography," *Nano Lett.* **14**, 2907–2913 (2014).
- ³⁸P. A. D. Gonçalves, E. Dias, Y. V. Bludov, and N. Peres, "Modeling the excitation of graphene plasmons in periodic grids of graphene ribbons: An analytical approach," *Phys. Rev. B* **94**, 195421 (2016).
- ³⁹I. J. Luxmoore, C. H. Gan, P. Q. Liu, F. Valmorra, P. Li, J. Faist, and G. R. Nash, "Strong coupling in the far-infrared between graphene plasmons and the surface optical phonons of silicon dioxide," *ACS Photonics* **1**, 1151–1155 (2014).
- ⁴⁰H. Yan, T. Low, W. Zhu, Y. Wu, M. Freitag, X. Li, F. Guinea, P. Avouris, and F. Xia, "Damping pathways of mid-infrared plasmons in graphene nanostructures," *Nat. Photonics* **7**, 394–399 (2013).
- ⁴¹J. Christensen, A. Manjavacas, S. Thongrattanasiri, F. H. Koppens, and F. J. García de Abajo, "Graphene plasmon waveguiding and hybridization in individual and paired nanoribbons," *ACS Nano* **6**, 431–440 (2012).
- ⁴²A. Y. Nikitin, F. Guinea, F. J. Garcia-Vidal, and L. Martin-Moreno, "Surface plasmon enhanced absorption and suppressed transmission in periodic arrays of graphene ribbons," *Phys. Rev. B* **85**, 081405 (2012).
- ⁴³E. Hwang and S. D. Sarma, "Screening-induced temperature-dependent transport in two-dimensional graphene," *Phys. Rev. B* **79**, 165404 (2009).
- ⁴⁴P. Y. Huang, C. S. Ruiz-Vargas, A. M. Van Der Zande, W. S. Whitney, M. P. Levendorf, J. W. Kevek, S. Garg, J. S. Alden, C. J. Hustedt, Y. Zhu *et al.*, "Grains and grain boundaries in single-layer graphene atomic patchwork quilts," *Nature* **469**, 389–392 (2011).
- ⁴⁵J. Heo, H.-J. Chung, S.-H. Lee, H. Yang, D. Seo, J. Shin, U.-I. Chung, S. Seo, E. Hwang, and S. D. Sarma, "Nonmonotonic temperature dependent transport in graphene grown by chemical vapor deposition," *Phys. Rev. B* **84**, 035421 (2011).
- ⁴⁶S. Doukas, P. Mensz, N. Myoung, A. C. Ferrari, I. Goykhman, and E. Lidorikis, "Thermionic graphene/silicon Schottky infrared photodetectors," *Phys. Rev. B* **105**, 115417 (2022).
- ⁴⁷M. Massicotte, P. Schmidt, F. Viaila, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, K.-J. Tielrooij, and F. H. Koppens, "Photo-thermionic effect in vertical graphene heterostructures," *Nat. Commun.* **7**, 12174 (2016).
- ⁴⁸A. D. Bartolomeo, "Graphene Schottky diodes: An experimental review of the rectifying graphene/semiconductor heterojunction," *Phys. Rep.* **606**, 1–58 (2016).
- ⁴⁹D. Sinha and J. U. Lee, "Ideal graphene/silicon Schottky junction diodes," *Nano Lett.* **14**, 4660–4664 (2014).
- ⁵⁰H. Yang, J. Heo, S. Park, H. J. Song, D. H. Seo, K.-E. Byun, P. Kim, I. Yoo, H.-J. Chung, and K. Kim, "Graphene barristor, a triode device with a gate-controlled Schottky barrier," *Science* **336**, 1140–1143 (2012).
- ⁵¹Y. An, A. Behnam, E. Pop, and A. Ural, "Metal-semiconductor-metal photodetectors based on graphene/p-type silicon Schottky junctions," *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **102**, 013110 (2013).
- ⁵²D. Tomer, S. Rajput, L. Hudy, C. Li, and L. Li, "Carrier transport in reverse-biased graphene/semiconductor Schottky junctions," *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **106**, 173510 (2015).
- ⁵³E. J. Dias, R. Yu, and F. J. G. de Abajo, "Thermal manipulation of plasmons in atomically thin films," *Light* **9**, 1–11 (2020).
- ⁵⁴X. Guo, H. Hu, B. Liao, X. Zhu, X. Yang, and Q. Dai, "Perfect-absorption graphene metamaterials for surface-enhanced molecular fingerprint spectroscopy," *Nanotechnology* **29**, 184004 (2018).
- ⁵⁵Y. Hu, Á. I. López-Lorente, and B. Mizaikoff, "Graphene-based surface enhanced vibrational spectroscopy: Recent developments, challenges, and applications," *ACS Photonics* **6**, 2182–2197 (2019).
- ⁵⁶R. Adato, A. Artar, S. Erramilli, and H. Altug, "Engineered absorption enhancement and induced transparency in coupled molecular and plasmonic resonator systems," *Nano Lett.* **13**, 2584–2591 (2013).
- ⁵⁷N. J. Barez, K. K. Gopalan, R. Alani, B. Paulillo, and V. Pruneri, "Mid-infrared gas sensing using graphene plasmons tuned by reversible chemical doping," *ACS Photonics* **7**, 879–884 (2020).
- ⁵⁸T. L. Myers, R. G. Tonkyn, T. O. Danby, M. S. Taubman, B. E. Bernacki, J. C. Birnbaum, S. W. Sharpe, and T. J. Johnson, "Accurate measurement of the optical constants n and k for a series of 57 inorganic and organic liquids for optical modeling and detection," *Appl. Spectrosc.* **72**, 535–550 (2018).
- ⁵⁹S. Ryu, L. Liu, S. Berciaud, Y.-J. Yu, H. Liu, P. Kim, G. W. Flynn, and L. E. Brus, "Atmospheric oxygen binding and hole doping in deformed graphene on a SiO₂ substrate," *Nano Lett.* **10**, 4944–4951 (2010).
- ⁶⁰A. Pirkle, J. Chan, A. Venugopal, D. Hinojos, C. Magnuson, S. McDonnell, L. Colombo, E. Vogel, R. Ruoff, and R. Wallace, "The effect of chemical residues on the physical and electrical properties of chemical vapor deposited graphene transferred to SiO₂," *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **99**, 122108 (2011).
- ⁶¹S. M. Sze and K. K. Ng, *Physics of Semiconductor Devices*, 3rd ed. (Wiley-Interscience, Hoboken, NJ, 2007).
- ⁶²A. Taflov and S. C. Hagness, "Computational Electrodynamics: The Finite-Difference Time-Domain Method," 3rd ed. (Artech House, 2005).
- ⁶³S. Doukas, A. Chatzilari, A. Dagkli, A. Papagiannopoulos, and E. Lidorikis, "Deep and fast free-space electro-absorption modulation in a mobility-independent graphene-loaded Bragg resonator," *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **113**, 011102 (2018).

- ⁶⁴M. Romagnoli, V. Soriano, M. Midrio, F. H. Koppens, C. Huyghebaert, D. Neumaier, P. Galli, W. Templ, A. D'Errico, and A. C. Ferrari, "Graphene-based integrated photonics for next-generation datacom and telecom," *Nat. Rev. Mater.* **3**, 392–414 (2018).
- ⁶⁵T. Fang, A. Konar, H. Xing, and D. Jena, "Mobility in semiconducting graphene nanoribbons: Phonon, impurity, and edge roughness scattering," *Phys. Rev. B* **78**, 205403 (2008).
- ⁶⁶G. W. Hanson, "Dyadic Green's functions and guided surface waves for a surface conductivity model of graphene," *J. Appl. Phys.* **103**, 064302 (2008).
- ⁶⁷L. Falkovsky, "Optical properties of graphene," *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* **129**, 012004 (2008).
- ⁶⁸See <https://www.lumerical.com/products/fdtd/> for "Lumerical solutions, Inc."
- ⁶⁹R. Lord and T. McCubbin, "Infrared spectroscopy from 5 to 200 microns with a small grating spectrometer," *J. Opt. Soc. Am.* **47**, 689–697 (1957).
- ⁷⁰A. Tomadin, D. Brida, G. Cerullo, A. C. Ferrari, and M. Polini, "Nonequilibrium dynamics of photoexcited electrons in graphene: Collinear scattering, Auger processes, and the impact of screening," *Phys. Rev. B* **88**, 035430 (2013).
- ⁷¹D. Brida, A. Tomadin, C. Manzoni, Y. J. Kim, A. Lombardo, S. Milana, R. R. Nair, K. S. Novoselov, A. C. Ferrari, G. Cerullo *et al.*, "Ultrafast collinear scattering and carrier multiplication in graphene," *Nat. Commun.* **4**, 1987 (2013).
- ⁷²M. Lazzeri, S. Piscanec, F. Mauri, A. Ferrari, and J. Robertson, "Electron transport and hot phonons in carbon nanotubes," *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **95**, 236802 (2005).
- ⁷³N. Bonini, M. Lazzeri, N. Marzari, and F. Mauri, "Phonon anharmonicities in graphite and graphene," *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **99**, 176802 (2007).
- ⁷⁴E. A. Pogna, X. Jia, A. Principi, A. Block, L. Banszerus, J. Zhang, X. Liu, T. Sohier, S. Forti, K. Soundarapandian *et al.*, "Hot-carrier cooling in high-quality graphene is intrinsically limited by optical phonons," *ACS Nano* **15**, 11285 (2021).
- ⁷⁵J. Viljas and T. Heikkilä, "Electron-phonon heat transfer in monolayer and bilayer graphene," *Phys. Rev. B* **81**, 245404 (2010).
- ⁷⁶R. Bistritzer and A. H. MacDonald, "Electronic cooling in graphene," *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **102**, 206410 (2009).
- ⁷⁷J. C. Song, M. Y. Reizer, and L. S. Levitov, "Disorder-assisted electron-phonon scattering and cooling pathways in graphene," *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **109**, 106602 (2012).
- ⁷⁸J. C. Song and L. S. Levitov, "Energy flows in graphene: Hot carrier dynamics and cooling," *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter* **27**, 164201 (2015).
- ⁷⁹A. Betz, S. H. Jhang, E. Pallecchi, R. Ferreira, G. Fève, J.-M. Berroir, and B. Plaçais, "Supercollision cooling in undoped graphene," *Nat. Phys.* **9**, 109–112 (2013).
- ⁸⁰M. W. Graham, S.-F. Shi, D. C. Ralph, J. Park, and P. L. McEuen, "Photocurrent measurements of supercollision cooling in graphene," *Nat. Phys.* **9**, 103–108 (2013).
- ⁸¹M. Massicotte, G. Soavi, A. Principi, and K.-J. Tielrooij, "Hot carriers in graphene—fundamentals and applications," *Nanoscale* **13**, 8376–8411 (2021).
- ⁸²J. F. Rodriguez-Nieva, M. S. Dresselhaus, and J. C. Song, "Enhanced thermionic-dominated photoresponse in graphene Schottky junctions," *Nano Lett.* **16**, 6036–6041 (2016).
- ⁸³S. Piscanec, M. Lazzeri, F. Mauri, A. Ferrari, and J. Robertson, "Kohn anomalies and electron-phonon interactions in graphite," *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **93**, 185503 (2004).
- ⁸⁴A. C. Ferrari, J. C. Meyer, V. Scardaci, C. Casiraghi, M. Lazzeri, F. Mauri, S. Piscanec, D. Jiang, K. S. Novoselov, S. Roth *et al.*, "Raman spectrum of graphene and graphene layers," *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **97**, 187401 (2006).
- ⁸⁵A. C. Ferrari, "Raman spectroscopy of graphene and graphite: Disorder, electron-phonon coupling, doping and nonadiabatic effects," *Solid State Commun.* **143**, 47–57 (2007).
- ⁸⁶E. Pop, V. Varshney, and A. K. Roy, "Thermal properties of graphene: Fundamentals and applications," *MRS Bull.* **37**, 1273–1281 (2012).
- ⁸⁷G. Luongo, A. D. Bartolomeo, F. Giubileo, C. A. Chavarin, and C. Wenger, "Electronic properties of graphene/p-silicon Schottky junction," *J. Phys. D* **51**, 255305 (2018).
- ⁸⁸M. Javadi, A. Noroozi, A. Mazaheri, and Y. Abdi, "Sequentially assembled graphene layers on silicon, the role of uncertainty principles in graphene-silicon Schottky junctions," *Adv. Opt. Mater.* **7**, 1900470 (2019).
- ⁸⁹M. Trushin, "Theory of thermionic emission from a two-dimensional conductor and its application to a graphene-semiconductor Schottky junction," *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **112**, 171109 (2018).
- ⁹⁰Y. S. Ang, L. Cao, and L. K. Ang, "Physics of electron emission and injection in two-dimensional materials: Theory and simulation," *InfoMat* **3**, 502–535 (2021).